

PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF HUMOR IN CROSS CULTURES

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Abstract: This article presents comprehensive analysis of humor used in communication taking into consideration pragmatic aspects. In addition to having a strong linguistic pragmatic quality, humor may also display traits and patterns from several levels. In addition to being strongly linked to the fundamental rules of language, comedy also heavily depends on how language is used in various settings. Pragmatics investigates the use of language in certain contexts, focusing in particular on the norms for using and understanding language in a variety of language-communicative settings.

1. Introduction:

Pragmatics is an important branch of linguistics in the English language. It helps us look beyond the literal meaning of words and utterances and allows us to focus on how meaning is constructed in specific contexts. When we communicate with other people, there is a constant negotiation of meaning between the listener and the speaker. Pragmatics looks at this negotiation and aims to understand what people mean when they communicate with each other.

Philosopher Charles Morris is credited with coining the word "pragmatics." He compares semantics and syntax with pragmatics. He claims that syntax is the study of the grammatical relations of linguistic units to one another and the grammatical structures of phrases and sentences that result from these grammatical relations, while semantics is the study of the relationship between linguistic units and the objects they denote. Pragmatics is the study of the relationship between linguistic units and people who communicate. Pragmatics is concerned with the intentional behaviors of speakers at particular times and places, typically involving language, as well as with the utterances used to denote particular events. Logic and semantics frequently deal with features of kinds of expressions, as opposed to qualities that vary from token to token, use to usage, or utterance to utterance and depend on the particular traits that distinguish them. Dealing with the consequences of context is one way that pragmatics is sometimes described. If all the facts that might differ from utterance to utterance are generally referred to as "context," then this is similar to saying that it deals with utterances. But one needs to take caution because the phrase is frequently employed in more constrained ways. (Martin, R.A. 2007) In pragmatics, we only pay attention to spoken language, conversations, or the ways in which people express themselves verbally or nonverbally when they interact with others. People convey a range of things about their culture, society, and other topics, including their feelings, desires, points of view, and more. However, there are instances when they are unable to communicate all of their aspirations for a number of reasons, such as fear, inferiority, disrespect, etc. Pragmatics makes an effort to understand how language may be used to examine human people in terms of their characteristics, needs, wants, attitudes, volition or volatile personalities, and many other things. As a result, pragmatics is the study of language as it is used by actual people in actual situations.

According to David Crystal (professor of linguistics at the University of Wales) in the book, *A Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics*:

Pragmatics is the study of language from the perspective of users, particularly of the decisions they make, the barriers they face while using language in social interaction, and the consequences their language usage has on other people who are involved in the act of communication..

The relative quality of the language employed and the speaker's aim toward the listener determine meaning. When we discuss relative distance, we are discussing how far one person is from another and how language conveys this distance. The study of pragmatics focuses on the relationship between what is said and what is understood by the listener. The first and most important step that has to be made is to distinguish between the meaning of sentences and the meaning of utterances. An utterance is a full unit of

communication that is naturally divided into breaths or pauses, or, to put it another way, by the speaker's silence. There is no exact linguistic definition for utterance. An utterance is a segment of speech that is silence-bound phonologically. Each 'turn' a speaker makes during a conversation may be regarded as an utterance.

2. Methodology.

The study of the actual language material was carried out using the complex methods including:

- analytical and descriptive during the presenting the concept of humor and pragmatics in linguistics;
- the method of contrastive analysis of the different humors taking into consideration pragmatic features;
- distributional analysis is used to explore the usage of humor in communication and their pragmatic analysis;

3. Practical outcome of the article consists that its rules and conclusions can be used in educational process, in particular on seminar and lecture employment on lexicology, stylistics of modern English language and can appear useful in practice of teaching of English language, in view of a communicative orientation of a modern universities.

4. Theoretical outcome of the article is technical material and samples of the deep analysis of humor used in communication taking into consideration pragmatic features. Especially the material and the result of the given Qualification paper may be used for practical lessons at universities practice the Linguistic courses.

5. Conclusion

Despite the fact that study on humor is undertaken within several scientific fields and paradigms, this social-humanitarian phenomena nevertheless has specific relevance and research significance at the moment and requires substantial interdisciplinary investigation. In particular, it necessitates a more in-depth analysis of verbal mechanisms for humor actualization, demonstrating how existing discursive models perform best in multivariate analyses of these models, and identifying the prerequisites and sufficient grounds for producing humorous effect in various types of discourse. A contextual rethinking of actual concepts, humor suggests an alternative, playful view of everyday reality, "communicative action in play," and is not only one of the most alluring discursive strategies for the aesthetic construction of statements, which invariably evoke laughter and thus a good mood in the addressee.

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